

A Study on the Effectiveness of Services Provided to Private Banking Customers of ICICI Bank, Thiruvalla

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Abstract

The study is mainly to find out the effectiveness of services provided to Private Banking customers of ICICI Bank, Thiruvalla. This is done by finding out the awareness level, usage and satisfaction of all the products and facilities provided to Private Banking customers. The research study conducted is descriptive and the population for this study is 148. Primary data is collected to meet the requirements. For collecting the data, a structured questionnaire method is used as an instrument. The questionnaire is based on multiple choice and close-ended questions. The study is mainly based on the primary data and the required primary data were collected through the structured questionnaire from 148 respondents. In this study, simple percentage and weighted Average is used to interpret the data collected. The difficulty encountered while conducting the survey was time constraint difficulty in getting appointments of Private Banking customers and internal banking restrictions do curtail my ability in meeting all customers within the given time.

Introduction

Company Profile

History

ICICI was formed in 1955 at the initiative of the World Bank, the Government of India and representatives of Indian industry. The Principal objective was to create a development financial institution for providing medium-term and long-term project financing to Indian businesses. In the 1990's, ICICI transformed its business from a development financial institution offering only project finance to a diversified financial services group offering a wide variety of products and services, both directly and through some subsidiaries and affiliates like ICICI Bank. In 1999, ICICI Bank became the first Indian company and the first bank or financial institution from Non-Japan Asia to be listed on the NYSE.

Product Profile

ICICI Bank Private Banking offers a comprehensive range of products & services:

Fixed Deposits

ICICI Bank offers competitive interest rates with the added comfort of safety and liquidity. The customer can also avail of loans against fixed deposits (up to 90%) at attractive rates.

Debit Cards & Credit Cards

The customer can avail a free personalized photo signature international debit card with enhanced cash withdrawal and point of sales limits. Also, the customer can also apply for the ICICI Bank Gold Credit Card, which comes with pre-approved limits.

Home Loans

The customer can enjoy attractive interest rates and the convenience of doorstep service from inquiry to disbursement. The facility to transfer customers existing higher interest rate loan to ICICI Bank is also available personal loans. Personal Loans are given without any collateral, security, and guarantor and reasons for the end use of funds. A balance and transfer facility is also available.

Auto Loans

ICICI Bank enjoys the preferred financier status with 12 leading manufacturers /dealers and has special tie-ups with most manufacturers – dealers to ensure the highest quality service to the customers.

Exclusive Phone Banking

A call from customers registered mobile to ICICI Bank Customer Care center would directly connect them to the Private Banking phone banking officer. No further authentication would be required for customers' non-financial transactions. It also provides customers with a dedicated toll-free number.

Internet Banking & Mobile Banking

ICICI Bank Internal Banking service is a convenient remote banking facility that uses sophisticated, multilayered security architecture with digital certification, to prevent unauthorized access Mobile banking keeps customers informed through regular mobile alerts.

Private Banking

Private Banking is a status given to the customers who can maintain a minimum balance account of Rs. 5,00,000 (saving + FD Balance) For the privileged Private Banking Clients ICICI Bank offers the entire range of products and services. This is delivered through a single point contact and a separate interaction area in the branch to ensure the highest quality service. Private Banking customers and would help them in improving these services.

Research Methodology

Type of Research Design

A research design is purely and simply a framework or a plan for study that guides is a collection of data. The descriptive research design is adopted for analyzing the data.

Sampling Design

The Private Banking customers of ICICI Bank Thiruvilla branch are the targeted respondents for the study. The population size is 148.

Sampling Frame

The frame refers to the customers who have been given Private Banking status by ICICI Bank, Thiruvalla.

Data Collection Method

Data collection is the most impeccable aspects in the research methodology. The data was collected based on interview technique and personally handed out structured questionnaire questions were resented is the same words is the same order to all the respondents.

The questionnaire was conceived in such a way that the questions, as well as the answers, were standardized. This is accomplished by employing a fixed alternative. Such a questionnaire facilitates easy administration & tabulation and analysis closed-ended questionnaire was used in the project.

Feature of Questionnaire

The questionnaire was designed to check those features.

- Awareness of Private Banking status
- Usage level of Private Banking facilities
- Awareness of various facilities provided to Private Banking Customers
- Satisfaction level of Private Banking Customers

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- Satisfaction level of Private Banking Customers

Statistical Tools Used

In the study, simple percentage and weighted Average is used to interpret the data collected

Analysis And Interpretation

The collected data is analyzed through simple percentage, Weighted Average and charts are used to interpret the data. The inferences given below the table will make the reader understand the problem as well as the solution to the problem.

Table 1 Table Showing The Respondents Banking Relationship With ICICI Bank

Banking Relationship	Percentage
Less than one year	46
1 to 2years	34
2 to 3 years	20

Interpretation

46% of the respondents are related with ICICI for less than a year, 34% for 1 to 2 years, and 20% for 2 to 3 years.

Table 2 Chart Showing Significance of Various Reasons to Bank

The significance of various reasons	Extremely Significant	Very Significant	Significant	Least Significant	Insignificant
Convenience	6	38	40	16	-
Customer Service	18	62	20	-	-
Facilities	12	20	56	12	-
Interest Rate	6	30	18	40	6
Security	12	40	48	-	-
Trust	18	32	24	20	6

6% of the respondents see Convenience as extremely significant, 38% feel it as very significant, 40% see it as significant and 16% feel it as a least significant reason to bank with ICICI. 18% of the respondents see Customer service as extremely significant, 62% feel it as very significant and 20% see it as a significant reason to bank with ICICI.

12% of the respondents see Facilities as extremely significant, 20% feel it as very significant, 56% see it as significant and 12% feel it as the least significant reason to bank with ICICI. 6% of the respondents see Interest rate as extremely significant, 30% feel it as very significant, 18% see it as significant, 40% feel it as least significant and 6% see it as an insignificant reason to bank with ICICI. 12% of the respondents see Security as extremely significant, 40% feel it as very significant and 48% see it as a significant reason to bank with ICICI. 18% of the respondents see Trust as extremely significant, 32% feel it as very significant, 24% see it as significant, 20% feel it as least significant and 6% see it as an insignificant reason to bank with ICICI.

Table 3 Table Showing Respondents Awareness of Private Banking Status

Awareness of Private Banking Status	Percentage
Yes	100
No	-

Interpretation

Among the respondents, 100% are aware of the Private Banking status

Table 5 Chart Showing Respondents' Frequency of Using Different Channels for Banking with ICICI Bank

ATM	75	320	123	24	-	542
Branch	-	72	204	124	-	400
Internet Banking	195	36	-	200	-	431
Mobile Banking	45	132	27	194	-	398
Phone Banking	45	36	45	230	-	356
Relationship	75	120	123	78	23	419

Interpretation

From the table, it is found that the most frequently used channel for banking with ICICI is through ATM. The next frequently used channels are Internet Banking, Relationship Officer, Branch, Mobile Banking, and Phone Banking respectively. It is found that Phone Banking is the least frequently used the channel for banking with ICICI.

Chart 5 Chart Showing Respondents' Frequency of Using Different Channels for Banking with ICICI Bank

Table 6 Satisfaction Level of Respondents on the Privileged Banking Services

Weight Ages Given

Highly Satisfied = 5

Satisfied = 4

Uncertain = 3

Dissatisfied = 2

Highly Dissatisfied = 1

Services Satisfied	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Uncertain	Dis Satisfied	Total
Avoiding charges	150	152	240	-	542
Better loan deals	45	284	132	48	509
Dedicated relationship officer	295	260	72	-	627
Enhanced withdrawal facility	165	284	132	-	581
Foreign exchange	-	164	294	18	476
Gold credit card	105	200	231	-	536
Investment options	30	484	27	24	565
Locker facility	130	96	294	-	520
Mobile banking	-	296	195	18	509
Phone banking	-	164	285	24	473

Interpretation

From the table, it is found that Dedicated relationship officer is the most satisfied privileged banking services. The next satisfied privileged banking services are Enhanced withdrawal facility, Investment options, Avoiding charges, Gold credit card, Locker facility, Better loan deals, Mobile banking, Phone banking, and Foreign exchange respectively. It is found that Foreign exchange is the least satisfied privileged banking services.

Chart 7 Chart Showing the Privileged Banking Services Availed by the Respondents

Conclusion

From the survey, it is understood that the awareness, usage and satisfaction level of Private Banking customers is quite low. It is also clear that customers have different needs, so they adhere to limited facilities provided to them. Also, the area such as increasing the effectiveness of privileges provided to Private Banking customers is to adhere.

Questionnaire

Name
 Contact no.
 Address

 Date

1. How long have you been banking with ICICI Bank?
 Less Than one year 1 to 2years 2 to 3 years More than three years

2. What are the reasons for banking with ICICI Bank? Can you please give the degree of significance of each?

	Extremely Significant	Very Significant	Significant	Least Significant	Insignificant
Convenience	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Customer Service	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Facilities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Interest Rate	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Security	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Trust	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Others	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Are you aware of your private banking status?

Yes No

4. What are the different channels used for banking with ICICI Bank?

<input type="checkbox"/> ATM	<input type="checkbox"/> Branch	<input type="checkbox"/> Internet Banking
<input type="checkbox"/> Mobile Banking	<input type="checkbox"/> Phone Banking	<input type="checkbox"/> Relationship Officer

5. Which of the privileged banking services provided by ICICI, have you availed? Kindly recognize them.

	Availed	Not Availed
Avoiding charges	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Better loan deals	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dedicated relationship officer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Enhanced withdrawal facility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Foreign exchange	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Gold credit card	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Investment options	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Locker facility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mobile banking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Phone banking	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Thank you for spending your precious time and effort in contributing towards the success of this research.

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www.icicibank.com

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